

HOSPITable: Domestication of healthcare

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Abstract The hospital is the traditional and familiar controlled environment where healthcare is defined and delivered. However the consequences of an older society the escalating costs of healthcare services and a shortage of personnel and facilities have put pressure on the healthcare system to deliver more support and treatments on an outpatient basis and in peoples home. The home and the hospital bring together very different cultural practices and environments and this inexorable geographical shift in care has potential impact on our physical and emotional relationship with our home space – our domain. These cultural practices/experiences can be mediated through objects, which in turn can provide vehicles through which to gain understanding of the richness and complexity of people's lives. The authors draw on the value of 'thinking with things' as a methodology. Central to this approach is the notion of 'exhibition' as a research tool that becomes a meeting space that enables this methodology to be applied. The 'exhibition' provides a theatre for conversation and offers the medium and method for discourse, data collection creating the conduit, through which societal assumptions relating to ageing and healthcare care can be made visible, explored and challenged.

Keywords *Design, Healthcare, Critical artefacts, Aesthetics, Exhibition as research*

Introduction

The challenges society faces in providing future healthcare suggests radical changes to the way health services are delivered and the way we engage with them. There is recognition that this is likely to demand more self-management and a shift of care from the hospital to our home. Home has different meanings for people but it is generally agreed to be a place of comfort, security and emotional well-being. It is a private place that reflects our identity with who we choose to share. It is where we live and where most people would prefer to die.

'Italy: The New Domestic Landscape' an exhibition at MOMA (Museum of Modern Art, New York) in 1972 was a seminal moment in Design history. A series of prototype environments and installations by leading Italian designers would reflect upon changing domestic living patterns within contemporary society. This hypothetical existence included "permanent nomadism," "life without objects," and "life without work. The exhibition is generally regarded as a statement that design in Italy was moving beyond being an applied art and was becoming a language capable of making a commentary on reality. While we have witnessed much of the prophecy of the exhibition of 1972, the domestic landscape is once again the site of radical change impacted by the inevitable changes in the environmental and contextual shift of our healthcare services. This paper describes a methodological approach employed by the authors that explores the role of critical artefacts and their use as physical metaphors to prompt discussion that may help inform our understanding and emotional relationship with this new hybrid ambiguous

landscape. We will briefly discuss how future care at home might challenge the symbolic meaning and relationships within our home and its object infrastructure.

Context

Foucault (Foucault 1963) described the 'medical gaze' where the hospitalised individual becomes a patient, then an object, through the practices of medicine. Foucault argues that the hospital was organised as an 'examining apparatus' enabling almost constant observation of the patient. In this creation all extraneous variables such as the home environment, family, friends and usual activities were excluded, the hospital providing the ideal laboratory setting where the causes of symptoms could be isolated and the effects of treatment monitored. Gardner (Gardner 2000) warns the ambience and safety of the home can potentially be shattered by the invasion of illness-related technology. The invasion of the technology of acute care into the home has the potential to destroy the nurturing and therapeutic environment of home as a means of promoting health recovery. He states while care of the sick in their homes invariably and increasingly brings with it technology, this technology needs to fit into the home environment without dominating it and transferring the anti-therapeutic culture of the hospital environment into the home. He advocates a need to develop sensitivity to the space of the home as one of sanctuary with multiple social and emotional functions that serve to increase the well-being of people in health and illness.

Milligan in her book, *'There's no place like home: Place and Care in an Ageing Society'* (Milligan 2009),

Figure 1. 'Future bathroom'. Older people engaging with 'things' related to bathroom activities to develop understanding of use.

describes the significance of the home as a social space and points to why healthcare providers may encounter resistance from people and their families in their attempt to reorganise domestic settings to accommodate the healthcare needs of the care recipients and to satisfy health and safety requirements (Phillipson 2007). She suggests that the desire to improvise or subvert the logics of care aids in order to retain a sense of home and ownership produces an ambiguity of place both for carer and care-recipient - one that brings home and care into tension as the aesthetics of health care systems jostle against the aesthetics of home. So while professional care support within the home may be beneficial to the informal carer and care recipient, they also transgress the social space of the home often creating change in the symbolic meaning of home.

The 'smart' house

The invisible nature of digital infrastructures into our homes in some way realises the vision of the New Domestic Landscape that presented a hypothetical life without objects. McGuirk (McGuirk 2015) discusses how the internet-of-things evangelists proclaim that it is the most 'disruptive' of phenomena and suggests 'the network is the new electricity' which itself was arguably one of the greatest environmental revolutions. This digital network provides real opportunity to deliver healthcare at home integrated into the new domestic landscape now often defined as the Smart house. The smart home is now becoming a reality with 84% of homes in the UK connected to the internet, an increase from 59% in 2006 (gov.uk) however the smart house is not the abstract aesthetic of 1972 but manifested within existing dated and diverse housing stock. England has one of the oldest dwelling stocks in Europe with 21% of dwellings built before 1919 and 16% built between 1919 and 1945. Much of the existing 26 million houses in the UK is expected to be standing in 2050 (gov.uk). The connected house, according to McGuirk, with a proliferation of smart, connected products that will turn the home into a prime data collection node, 'is becoming a data factory'. This data will be transmitted and stored by the manufacturers of these products and we will witness the erosion of privacy. This 'surveillance' might for example lead to patterns of

control, facilitate 'nudge' tactics to change our behavior and provide access to our state of health that may have implications on our personal insurance. Rem Koolhaas asserts, 'very soon your house will betray you'.

Thinking with things

If we are to assume a greater uptake of healthcare at home to relieve pressures on current systems of delivery we must not simply develop solutions and focus research within the narrow boundaries of healthcare. Solutions will only be successful if they fit with the complexity of our lives therefore there is value in taking everyday experiences as a starting point.

The authors draw on the value of 'thinking with things' as a method to build understanding of the factors end-users identify as being important. Current work builds on a series of projects, led and now briefly described by the authors, that develops and utilises artefacts that are presented not as solutions, but as vehicles through which to engage people, promote discussion, to raise questions, challenge preconceptions, illicit information and generate in-depth data.

Significant in the 'future bathroom' project (Chamberlain and Yoxall 2012) was the recruitment of older people who were involved from the outset and in every stage of the research and product development. The approach broke down the hierarchical relationship often created between designer and user, academic researcher and user and adopted a respect for the user as expert, designing 'with' users and not just 'for' them. The older community lay researchers undertook home visits to older people living in the community and were able to empathise and gather more intimate stories than would have emerged through more traditional research methods (e.g. questionnaires) or if the younger academic research team had conducted the visits. Public exhibitions to open discussion around activities that are normally considered taboo were curated by author 1 (Figure 1). These insights revealed not only physical challenges within the bathroom as one ages but emotionally complex relationships in caring for others. Milligan (2009)

Figure 2. Stigmas a collection of furniture (author 1) that portrays and landscape of old age and part of the engaging series of exhibitions and workshops. Far left : 'This is a chair to sit on' that reflects declining cognitive processing. Far right : 'Adjustable chair' that reflects that the crude adjustments often made to accommodate declining physical ability.

describes how as ageing in place shifts care and support back toward the home and how informal carers are once again taking on many of the routine tasks of caring for the aging body. This includes much of the intimate and personal tasks involved in care such as washing and bathing, dressing, toileting and feeding the care recipient. Helping an older relative to perform normally personal and private acts such as bathing and toileting, for example, gives rise to transgressions of contemporary social taboos around care in western society – particularly cross sex care. Wiles (2003) claims these aspects of intimate care can involve considerable physical and emotional distress for both carer and care recipient.

Engagingaging (Chamberlain and Craig 2013) adopted a methodology that uses objects and artefacts (Figure 2) to stimulate and scaffold thinking, offering valuable vehicles through which the complexities of lives can be understood. It provided a theatre for conversation and the medium and method for data collection and created the conduit, through which societal assumptions relating to ageing could be made visible, explored and challenged. Building on methods developed within engagingaging the principles of the traditional exhibition were distilled into a format that was more flexible, accessible and inclusive.

'Exhibition in a box' (Chamberlain and Craig 2013) took the essence of the exhibition into a suitcase, a la

Duchamp that could be transported to diverse environs including the home. In doing so the home was transformed into the research arena, providing individuals with a tangible prompt to scaffold conversation.

These boxes comprised of everyday objects, photographs and textual material defined through the user-workshops undertaken in conjunction with the earlier large-scale exhibitions in 'engagingaging'. The objects were carefully selected to code, represent and prompt further discussion on themes that had emerged from earlier research. The objects could and did combine to create objective correlatives enabling participants to express emotional responses (Figure 3).

The present study, Insights into Telehealth and Care Technologies (inTaCT) undertaken by the authors utilises and further tests this methodology exploring participatory methods and approaches to engage people who are frequently under-represented in telehealth/telecare research by virtue of their age, ethnicity or socio-economic status, in meaningful ways. The strength of the critical artefact methodology is that the objects transcend boundaries of culture, language and age and whilst the objects remain unchanging the associations and emotions they prompt and the stories they elicit are dynamic and ever changing.

Figure 3. Exhibition in distilled into a box. Objects prompting meaningful insights into daily life.

Figure 4. HOSPITaBLe Chamberlain (selection from a collection): Top Left - Google aid. Top Right - IV Lamp. Bottom - Grande Commode.

This first phase of the research was a feasibility study, focusing particularly on the methods of engagement. Prior to recruitment of participants, ethical approval was obtained, following which posters and invitations describing the research and inviting people who might be interested in taking part in a workshop/focus group exploring technology were distributed through a number of voluntary and third sector organizations. These included: Age UK, the Churches Council for Community Care and the Chinese Elders.

In total thirty-two socially and ethnically diverse community dwelling older people were recruited. Individuals were invited to attend one of four workshops that were held in community venues and were facilitated by the research team. It was not a requirement for participants to be users of telehealth or telecare devices since the aim was to develop a broader understanding of participants' attitudes to digital products and devices. Each workshop lasted on average for two hours and participants were invited, in turn, to select and to respond to the objects contained within exhibition in a box. This data was analysed using framework analysis (Ritchie and Spencer, 1994). This enabled the development of a matrix of themes and related sub-topics from the data as well as identification of the links across themes, different participants and venues.

Refining the question

The present generation of home health technologies and products are predicated on the assumption that end-users have already embraced the shift in the healthcare paradigm from the hospital to their home. An assumption is also made that designing more aesthetically appealing products will automatically increase engagement in these products and technologies. However early findings of this present study suggests that acceptance of digital health solutions is more complex. Lee (Lee 2010) describes an alternative to the art-centred model of aesthetics that includes functional beauty. For example a coffee

maker may be aesthetically appreciable based on how well it makes coffee. However portraying aesthetic appeal in relation to products that deal with very private, intimate and traumatic matters of our illness may be more challenging to successfully achieve a signal of functional beauty. Lee draws on Heidegger's work and writes, 'in dwelling we do more than just construct our homes. We stay with them, care for them, turn them into places of meaning and meaning-making; our aesthetic sense of the home arises in this process'.

The initial findings from inTaCT have informed 'HOSPITaBLe' a collection of furniture created by author 1 (Figure 4) that embraces this complexity, and the artefacts through exhibition integrated with a series of community workshops aims to makes sense of this meaning. The artefacts present a hybrid ambiguous landscape each positioning metaphorical questions within the context of our future healthcare.

This work builds on the approach postulated by the designers who contributed to the *New Domestic Landscape* where Design is employed 'as a language to make commentary'. The artefacts created as part of HOSPITaBLe present questions rather than solutions. Dunne & Raby (in Koshinen et al 2011) support the notion that 'Design that asks carefully crafted questions and makes us think is just as important as design that solves problems or finds answers'. Mathematician and philosopher Henri Poincare is quoted to have declared, "The question is not, 'What is the answer?' The question is 'What is the question?'" (Licklider 1960).

There are undoubtedly many potential benefits to healthcare delivery at home. Delivery of care at home is not actually new and half a century ago house calls from the doctor were common but we have since witnessed a dramatic decline of this service. Home healthcare could extend care and provide greater and easier access for the care recipient allowing a more

customized and personal care package. Where social control has historically been the feature of hospitals we may see a rebalance of power when the patient is in the familiarity of their domestic environs. However more research is needed to explore how we negotiate the emotional complexity of what we understand as a home and what in more recent history has been institutionalized, a place for healthcare.

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